

Appendix

Individual Work Pricing by Non-fungible Personal Tokens (“NFT Gig Tokens”) – a New Opportunity for Gig Workers (Kamilla Marchewka-Bartkowiak, Michał Litwiński, and Karolina Nowak – corresponding author: karolina.nowak@ue.poznan.pl)

Table 12.6. Classification of services provided by personal token issuers, according to Kässä and Lehdonvirta (2018)

Class of services	Examples of provided services
Professional services - P	Accounting
	Consulting
	Financial planning
	Legal services
	Human resources
	Project management
Clerical and data entry - CD	Customer service
	Data entry
	Transcription
	Tech support
	Web research
	Virtual assistant
Creative and multimedia - CM	Animation
	Architecture
	Audio
	Logo design
	Photography
	Presentations
	Video production
	Voide acting
Sales and marketing support - SM	Ad posting
	Lead generation
	Search engine optimisation
	Telemarketing
Software development and technology - ST	Data science
	Game development
	Mobile development
	QA and testing
	Server maintenance
	Software development
	Web development
	Web scraping
Writing and translation - WT	Academic writing
	Article writing
	Copywriting
	Creative writing
	Technical writing
Translation	

Source: Kässä and Lehdonvirta (2018).

Table 12.7. Type of services, according to classification by Kässi and Lehdonvirta

Class of services	Number of cases	Percentage
Professional services	63	37.06%
Creative and multimedia	30	17.65%
Software development and technology	27	15.88%
Clerical and data entry	22	12.94%
Sales and marketing support	5	2.94%
Writing and translation	2	1.18%
Other	21	12.35%
Total	170	100%

Source: own calculations based on data from PT platform.

Table 12.8. Type of services provided by analysed 45 token issuers

Token name	Class of services
RAF	Financial/Economic F/E
DJM	Financial/Economic F/E
AWA	Financial/Economic F/E
RL	Financial/Economic F/E
MAZAK	Financial/Economic F/E
FK	Financial/Economic F/E
SKM	Financial/Economic F/E
VIP	Financial/Economic F/E
BEN	Social (community services) – S
ARTCOIN	Social (community services) – S
ZIBICOIN	Social (community services) – S
LSZ	Social (community services) – S
PAGEMAN	Social (community services) – S
PP	Social (community services) – S
POKATO	Social (community services) – S
DDT	Social (community services) – S
MEGA	Social (community services) – S
CYRIL	Social (community services) – S
SJW	Social (community services) – S
MTK	Social (community services) – S
POL	Social (community services) – S
MAC	Social (community services) – S
MH	Social (community services) – S
KRC	Social (community services) – S
SZUSTER	Social (community services) – S
GAB	Social (community services) – S
BOR	Social (community services) – S
SMIM	Social (community services) – S

CNSL	Social (community services) – S
JKCOIN	Technology – T
DEX	Technology – T
FULOFMO	Technology – T
GREG	Technology – T
CHAR	Technology – T
SECUREMB	Technology – T
HGT	Technology – T
SQL	Technology – T
ZBL	Technology – T
KGAJ	Technology – T
RSPT	Technology – T
RAW	Technology – T
SWADER	Technology – T
KERMAN	Technology – T
ASTO	Technology – T
MACK	Technology – T

Source: own calculations based on data from PT platform.

Table 12.9 Valuation of services and basic information on personal tokens

Token name	Number of months from PT issue	PT price [USD]	Number of PT/1 work hour	USD/1 work hour
VIP	34	0.000554	70,000	38.78
MTK	34	0.000044	10,000	0.44
BOR	35	0.009116	10,000	91.16
KERMAN	14	0.105116	7,500	788.37
CHAR	28	0.000466	6000	2.80
ZIBICOIN	32	0.000068	5000	0.34
GREG	34	0.250254	5000	1,251.27
FK	34	1.934937	5000	9,674.69
SKM	28	0.108603	5000	543.02
SWADER	33	0.000088	5000	0.44
SMIM	1	0.000093	4000	0.37
RAF	26	0.000266	3000	0.80
AWA	26	0.022151	3000	66.45
MEGA	27	0.000044	2500	0.11
FULOFMO	34	0.000091	2000	0.18
PAGEMAN	32	0.025276	2000	50.55
POKATO	35	0.020535	2000	41.07
DJM	29	0.147357	1200	176.83
JKCOIN	34	0.028854	1000	28.85
BEN	35	0.025276	1000	25.28
DDT	34	0.02735	1000	27.35
CYRIL	10	0.003351	1000	3.35
HGT	34	0.000066	1000	0.07

SJW	24	0.000532	1000	0.53
ZBL	13	0.000066	1000	0.07
KRC	33	0.005987	1000	5.99
RAW	18	0.000433	1000	0.43
MH	34	0.250254	800	200.20
MAC	32	0.00098	600	0,59
MAZAK	29	0.000088	500	0.04
POL	27	0.000066	500	0.03
SZUSTER	32	0.000022	400	0.01
RSPT	34	0.002279	400	0.91
KGAJ	34	0.250254	350	87.59
LSZ	35	0.009876	300	2.96
SQL	29	0.000621	200	0.12
GAB	25	0.000421	200	0.08
RL	35	0.012451	151	1.88
DEX	35	0.009876	100	0.99
ARTCOIN	34	0.00011	100	0.01
PP	34	0.020535	100	2.05
SECUREMB	34	0.00364	100	0.36
MACK	34	0.000113	100	0.01
ASTO	1	0.000023	3	0.00
CNSL	17	310.7645	1	310.76

* PT prices as on 30th June 2021

Source: own calculations based on data from PT platform.

Figure 12.4. Market price per 1 hour of individual work of PT owners and network (axiological) valuation (in a range from 1PT/1work hour to 1,200 PT/1work hour)

Source: own elaboration based on data from PT platform.

Figure 12.5. Market price per 1 hour of individual work of PT owners and network (axiological valuation (in a range from 2,000PT/1work hour to 10,000PT/1work hour)*)

* for a clearer graphical presentation the figure does not include the case with highest price per token – VIP tokens (70,000 tokens per 1 work hour)

Source: own elaboration based on data from PT platform.